

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

PEDAGOGICAL FUTUROLOGY AS A KEY FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATION

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Abstract

The aim of the study is to analyse and evaluate the role of pedagogical futurology in the development of education. The article discusses the significant role of pedagogical predictions in the development of education systems. It presents the key factors on which pedagogical predictions are based. The article extensively examines the methods and means that are used to predict the future of education.

Keywords: pedagogical futurology, educational development, globalization, factors, trends, prediction methods.

Introduction

This article discusses the significant role of pedagogical futurology in the development of education systems. It presents the key factors that form the basis of the pedagogical futurology predictions.

The article extensively examines various methods and means employed by pedagogical futurology to predict the future of education.

The aim of the study is to analyse and evaluate the importance of pedagogical futurology predictions in the development of education.

The degree of elaboration of the issue under discussion: Various Armenian and foreign experts, such as G. Harutyunyan, N.K. Harutyunyan, A.V. Khutorskoy, A. Naidysh, I.V. Bestuzhev-Lada, I. Wallerstein, Alvin Toffler, Michel Van der Wel, Peter Bishop, A. Turchin, and others have addressed the main issue and expressed their perspectives. Each idea and approach is uniquely interesting and valuable, contributing significantly to the research on the main issue.

Novelty: The significant role of pedagogical futurology in the development of educational systems has been analysed and emphasized. The key factors on which pedagogical futurology relies when developing educational predictions have been analysed.

Sociological surveys have been conducted among lecturers and students to assess the level of awareness regarding the role of pedagogical futurology predictions in education development.

In the 21st century, education has become increasingly dynamic and in demand. Contemporary technologies, globalization, and evolving social needs pose new challenges for educational systems. Within this context, the predictions of pedagogical futurology become an indispensable part of education development.

Pedagogical futurology is a scientific branch of pedagogy that studies the trends in educational development and develops strategies to adapt educational systems to changing conditions.

Pedagogical futurology integrates pedagogy, sociology, economics, and technology knowledge to predict educational development and scenarios.

By developing various scenarios about the likely developments in education, it must consider global political, financial, and ecological phenomena and the risks that could positively and negatively affect educational advancements in the future.

As Michel van der Wel states, “Futurology is about ‘a way of thinking’. I personally describe that way of thinking as a mix of a few elements: pick up weak signals of change; analyze clear and implied consequences of changes; see the big picture of changes at a system level” [7].

Pedagogical futurology explores the aims, objectives and directions of our movement in the field of education and the potential opportunities and difficulties that we may encounter.

Futurologists strive to anticipate future trends. The essence of studying the future is transitioning from a passive and deterministic understanding to an active and confident participation in building the preferred future.

“Humanity has always been fascinated by the future: the development of science, culture, economy, technology, social order, human potential, and education. Various methods have been and continue to be employed to make predictions: scientific, analytical, visionary, mystical, and more. But why do we need to know the future? Every prediction has a purpose. By conceptualizing the future, we define specific directions, decide on ways to achieve them, and seek the means to do so. In doing this, we change both the present and its imminent state. Herein lies the essence of prediction: the driving force of the present, the means to construct the future,” writes A.V. Khutorskoy [5].

O. V. Naidysh believes that “Futurological scenarios are valuable not so much for their ‘models of the future’ with specific content, as for how they reflect and express the current state of everyday consciousness. Under the broadest sense, futurology implies some intellectual movement that forms a system of knowledge about the future of humanity” [6].

According to N.K. Harutyunyan “Studying the future allows us to be better prepared for it, making informed decisions today and recognizing their consequences” [4].

Let us now analyse the role of pedagogical futurology in the field of education.

1. Predicts trends: Pedagogical futurology allows us to analyse current trends and anticipate future changes in the education field. It helps educational institutions adapt to the evolving needs of learners and the job market.

2. Develops Innovations: Based on predictions of the future, pedagogical futurology facilitates the development of innovative educational methodologies, technologies, and programs. It enables the implementation of more effective educational processes tailored to the needs of learners.

3. Helps Prepare for Future Challenges: With the aid of predictions of pedagogical futurology, educational institutions can prepare learners for future challenges, equipping them with the necessary knowledge, skills, and competencies. It will help graduates adapt to a rapidly changing world and succeed in their careers.

4. Facilitates Strategic Planning: Futurological analyses allow educational institutions to develop long-term development strategies and plan investments in the education field, considering future demands and challenges.

Pedagogical futurology relies on several factors when developing educational predictions.

1. The first factor is technological innovations. Advancements in new technologies, such as artificial intelligence, virtual reality, and the Internet, impact educational processes, teaching methodologies, and the accessibility of knowledge. Therefore, pedagogical futurology considers the role of technological innovations.

2. Another important factor is demographic changes. Changes within the population, such as an increase in the number of young or older people, migration flows, and changes in family structures, can influence the demands on education systems.

3. Economic Conditions: While making predictions, pedagogical futurology considers the state of the economy and the job market, as well as trends in employment and investment, which impact the education accessibility, its quality, and development directions of education.

4. Socio-cultural changes are also an important factor in making predictions. Changes in the socio-cultural field, including shifts in values, cultural trends, and demands related to civic education and intercultural understanding, shape the demands on education and its delivery methods.

5. Pedagogical futurology also considers **political and legal factors.** Government policy in the education field, legislative changes, financial support, and educational standards also influence the future predictions of education.

6. Global Trends and Challenges are viewed as very important factors. Global issues such as climate change, sustainable development, globalization, and

refugees distress necessitate new approaches to education and competency development to address these challenges effectively.

Considering these and many other factors, pedagogical predictions strives to anticipate educational development and adapt educational systems to the changing conditions and challenges of the future.

In his work *Future Shock*, American futurologist Alvin Toffler writes: “We must create a “Council of the Future” in every school and community: Teams of men and women devoted to probing the future in the interests of the present. By projecting “assumed futures,” by defining coherent educational responses to them, by opening these alternatives to active public debate, such councils—similar in some ways to the “prognostic cells” advocated by Robert Jungk of the Technische Hochschule in Berlin—could have a powerful impact on education” [8, 456].

I.V. Bestuzhev-Lada finds that “prediction does not amount to attempts at detailing the future. The predictor bases their work on the dialectical characteristics of future phenomena and the fact that necessity creates its path through contingencies and that addressing future phenomena requires a probabilistic approach, taking into account a wide array of possible options. Only such an approach makes it possible to effectively use the most probable, desirable, and optimal option to justify the goal, plan, programs, project, and decisions in general” [1].

The world is changing. New technologies alter our lives, our beliefs, and our values. Avoiding changes is not possible, but it is possible to make these changes positive.

According to G. Harutyunyan, “One of the primary challenges for states and national communities is the complex assessment of the current situation and the formation of certain conceptions about future developments. Currently, in the world's leading countries, there is a high demand for predictions and scenario developments, which have become an essential part of political culture” [3].

I. Wallerstein’s thoughts are also interesting: “The future is shaped through the complex network of interactions between the necessary, the normative, the essential, and the accidental, as well as the secondary and the chaotic. Therefore, identifying causal relationships in predictions is “super complex”. They possess a variable nature and imply the construction of numerous probable scenarios” [10].

Various methods and means to predict the future of education are employed by Pedagogical futurology.

Let us present an analytical overview of these ideas.

1. Data and Trend Analysis: Pedagogue-futurologists study current trends in education and analyse statistical data on the development of educational systems in various countries. This allows them to identify the main development directions and predict their future progression.

2. Expert Assessments: Pedagogical futurology employs expert evaluations and predictions of specialists in education, economics, sociology, and other fields regarding the future of education, which allows for the

consideration of various perspectives and the attainment of a more comprehensive understanding of potential development scenarios.

3. Scenario Planning: Pedagogical futurology utilizes scenario planning to develop alternative future scenarios for education based on different factors. These factors include technological innovations, demographic changes, economic trends, and socio-cultural developments.

4. Forecasting Models: Using forecasting models and computer simulations allows pedagogical futurology to predict future trends and study their impacts on education systems.

5. Delphi Method: This method involves surveys of experts aimed at achieving a consensus on future trends and events. These surveys' results help formulate more robust predictions and recommendations.

6. Monitoring New Technologies: Pedagogical futurology monitors new technologies' development and studies their potential for application in education. This includes exploring the impacts of virtual reality, emerging technologies, and artificial intelligence on learning processes.

These methods and means assist educational futurology in developing more precise and informed predictions about the future of education. These predictions, in turn, contribute to developing more effective strategic management in educational systems.

In his book *Futurology XXI Century: Immortality or Global Catastrophe*, Alexey Turchin writes: "The main driving force of the 21st century will be the development of three super-technologies: artificial intelligence, nanotechnology, and biotechnology, which can fundamentally transform society. As a result of such development, two scenarios are possible: either the radical extension of human life or global destruction" [9].

Pedagogical predictions help ensure a more efficient, quality, and contemporary education that meets the demands of the future, facilitating the preparation of specialists to address future challenges.

Equally thought-provoking are Peter Bishop's ideas in the article *Why Teach the Future*: "What should we teach students about change? To teach the future begins by helping students identify and classify change by source, level, horizon and rate. Change is the future. The future is born from change" [2].

To confirm the theoretical analysis of the article's central issue and assess the level of awareness of pedagogical futurology among lecturers and students, sociological surveys were conducted in various faculties of Yerevan State University. These sociological surveys included lecturers and students from the Pedagogy and Education Development Center, the Faculties of History, Theology, Russian Philology, and Faculty of European Languages and Communication.

The selection of faculties followed the principle of including one faculty of pedagogy and several faculties where the Pedagogy course is taught. A total of 162 respondents participated in the sociological surveys, including 24 lecturers and 138 students. The sociological surveys were anonymous.

The tools used for the sociological surveys were pre-designed questionnaires consisting of seven questions. The goal of the sociological surveys was to assess the level of awareness among lecturers and students regarding the importance of pedagogical futurology in the development of education.

Below is an analysis of the sociological surveys results, presented question by question. The data were processed using Google Forms.

Sociological Survey Results among Lecturers

The number of participating lecturers is 24.

Question 1: Are you aware of Pedagogical Futurology scientific branch?

The possible responses to the question are:

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) Partly

The responses to the first question were as follows: "yes" - 18 respondents (75%), "no" - 2 respondents (8.33%), "partly" - 4 respondents (16.6%). It is satisfying that most of the surveyed lecturers, 18 respondents (75%), are aware of Educational Futurology. This may be conditioned by the fact that most of the surveyed lecturers are from the Pedagogy and Education Development Center, who, as specialists in pedagogy, might be informed about the scientific branches of Pedagogy. As for the remaining six lecturers who responded "no" (8.33%) or "partly" (16.6%), this is likely conditioned by the fact that these lecturers are specialists in other fields.

Figure 1. Lecturers' Awareness of Educational Futurology

- a) Yes – 75 %
- b) No – 8.33 %
- c) Partly – 16.6 %

Question 2: Are you aware of the specific methods and approaches used for predicting the future of education at your university?

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) Partly

The following responses were given to this question: "yes" - 14 people (58.33%), "no" - 3 people (12.5%), "partly" - 7 people (29.16%).

The awareness (58.3%) and lack of awareness (41.66%) regarding the methods and approaches to predicting the future of education are almost evenly divided. This indicates that the university lecturers are not sufficiently informed about the development and

future-oriented predictions of education being implemented by themselves, a gap that could diminish the effectiveness of their activities. This gap needs to be filled with training sessions.

Figure 2. Lecturers' Awareness of Methods for Predicting the Future of Education

- a) Yes – 58.33%
- b) No – 12.5%
- c) Partly – 29.16%

Question 3: Have you noticed any changes in the educational process due to implementing predictive approaches?

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) Difficult to answer

The percentage distribution of responses to this question is as follows: "yes" - 15 lecturers (62.5%), "no" - 4 (16.66%), "difficult to answer" - 5 (20.83%).

What do these percentages indicate? They show that most surveyed lecturers are familiar with their institution's strategic development plan, where external factors, risks, and the institution's strengths and weaknesses are presented using the SWOT analysis method. This provides the opportunity to make predictions about the development of education and the future of education. It is concerning that 36% are unaware of this.

Figure 3. Lecture's Awareness of changes in the educational process due to implementing predictive approaches.

- a) Yes – 62.5 %
- b) No – 16.66 %
- c) Difficult to answer - 20.83 %

Question 4: What is your assessment of the effectiveness of applying predictions of pedagogical

futurology in the context of educational development?

- a) High
- b) Moderate
- c) Low

The responses to this question are distributed as follows: "high" - 12 lecturers (50%), "moderate" - 10 lecturers (41.6%), and "low" - 2 lecturers (8.33%).

These responses indicate that exactly half of the surveyed lecturers, 50%, believe in the effectiveness of pedagogical futurology predictions in the development of education, while the other half do not. What could this be conditioned by? According to us, this is because many lecturers are unaware of and do not participate in the educational reform process, which is also based on scientific predictions about education development.

Not participating in the reform process is either a sign of indifference or a lack of high competencies.

Figure 4. Lecturers' Assessment of the Effectiveness of Applying Educational Predictions

- a) High – 50%
- b) Moderate – 41.6 %
- c) Low - 8.33 %

Question 5: Do you think that pedagogical predictions help to adapt educational programs and methodologies to the demands of the modern world?

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) Partly

What is the distribution of responses to this question? Out of the 24 surveyed lecturers, 17 (70.83%) are confident that "yes", it helps, 1 (4.16%) says "no", and 6 (25%) believe it helps "partly".

Nearly 71% of the lecturers see the role of pedagogical futurology predictions in improving educational programs and methodologies, which is positive and encouraging. The number of those uncertain or sceptical is insignificant, only seven people. We believe these respondents are not directly involved in improving educational programs and methodologies.

Figure 5. Lecturers' Opinions on the Assistance of Pedagogical Predictions in Improving Educational Programs and Methodologies

- a) Yes – 70.83%
- b) No – 4.16 %
- c) Partly – 25 %

Question 6: Do you see any specific challenges and obstacles in the application of pedagogical futurology predicting approaches in the field of education?

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) Partly

The results are distributed as follows: 4 professors responded with "yes" (16.6%), "no" - 7 individuals (29.1%), and 13 responded with "partly" (54.16%).

The results indicate that out of the 24 surveyed professors, 20 do not believe that predictions can hinder education development; instead, they could preemptively address issues within the education field. The four "yes" responses, we assume, are due to a lack of information or mistrust.

Figure 6. Lecturers' opinions on specific barriers in the application of pedagogical futurology predicting approaches

- a) Yes – 16.6 %
- b) No- 29.1 %
- c) Partly – 54.16 %

Question 7: Are additional resources or support necessary for more practical application of predictive methods of pedagogical futurology in education?

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) Partly

The results are as follows: Out of the 24 surveyed professors, 19 (79.1%) believe that "yes", additional resources or support are necessary to apply educational predictions more effectively. This indicates confidence in the results provided by educational predictions. Only five individuals have doubts, which is due to their lack of awareness about the pedagogical predictions.

Figure 7. Lecturers' Opinions on the Need for Additional Resources or Support for More Effective Application of Predictive Methods in Education

- a) Yes – 79.1 %
- b) No- 4.16 %
- c) Partly – 16.6 %

The responses to sociological surveys on pedagogical predictions among lecturers lead to the conclusion that it is necessary to enhance lecturers' awareness of the critical role of pedagogical futurology predictions in the development process of education. This can be achieved through non-formal education, specifically through training courses.

Sociological Survey Results among Students

Sociological surveys have been conducted at Yerevan State University, specifically within Pedagogy and Education Development Center, the Faculties of History, Theology, Russian Philology, and European Languages and Communication, involving 138 students. The sociological surveys were conducted using a questionnaire prepared in advance consisting of 7 points. The sociological surveys are anonymous.

Question 1: Are you aware of Pedagogical Futurology scientific branch?

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) Partly

The responses to the survey among students regarding Pedagogical Futurology is distributed as follows: "yes" was answered by 51 of the surveyed 138 students (36.95%), "no" by 41 (29.7%), and "partly" by 46 (33.33%). The responses indicate that of the 138 surveyed students, 87, the majority, who answered "no" and "partly" are not aware of the Pedagogical Futurology scientific branch. Meanwhile, the 51 students who answered yes are unmistakably students of Pedagogy and Education Development Center and are enrolled in the course "Pedagogical Futurology" and are therefore well-informed about what the field entails. Regardless of their major, all students should be informed about an important factor contributing to education development in the 21st century: Pedagogical predictions.

Figure 8. Students' Awareness of Pedagogical Futurology

- a) Yes – 36, 95 %
- b) No – 29, 7 %
- c) Partly – 33, 33 %

Question 2: Are you aware of the specific methods and approaches used for predicting the future of education at your university?

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) Partly

The following responses were given: out of the surveyed 138 students, 51 (36.95%) answered "yes", 29 (21.01%) answered "no", and 58 (42.02%) answered "partly". The positive response from 51 students is again evident that they are students of the "Social Pedagogy" educational program, while the number of students who answered "no" has decreased to 29, compared to the first question about awareness of the Pedagogical Futurology field, where 41 students had answered "no". It seems inconsistent to be unaware of the field but be knowledgeable about its methods. Our opinion is that this is not objective. The increase in "partly" responses has occurred due to the decrease in "no" responses.

We believe it is essential to undertake additional courses related to Pedagogical Futurology for students of other faculties.

Figure 9. Students' Awareness of Methods for Predicting the Future of Education

- a) Yes – 36, 95 %
- b) No – 21,01%
- c) Partly - 42,04%

Question 3: Have you noticed any changes in the educational process due to implementing predictive approaches?

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) Difficult to answer

What responses have we received to this question? Out of the surveyed 138 students, 70 students (50.72%) answered "yes," 19 students (13.76%) answered "no," and 49 students (35.5%) were "struggling to answer."

It is gratifying that more than half of the surveyed students, 70 students, have noticed the changes primarily made based on educational predictions. However, it is concerning that the other half of the respondents, 68 students, have not noticed or are unaware of the changes being implemented in the educational process. This speaks not only to the students' unawareness but also to their indifference regarding the development of their education.

Figure 10. Students' Awareness of changes in the educational process due to implementing predictive approaches.

- a) Yes – 50.72 %
- b) No – 13.76 %
- c) Difficult to answer - 35.5 %

Question 4: What is your assessment of the effectiveness of applying predictions of pedagogical futurology in the context of educational development?

- a) High
- b) Moderate
- c) Low

The distribution of responses to this question is as follows: 33 students (23.91%) rated it "high", 98 students (71.01%) rated it "moderate", and 7 students (5.07%) rated it "low". Although half of the students had noticed changes in the previous question in the educational process, their assessment of the quality of those changes is not high in response to this question. They have shifted towards a "medium" rating. This also gives reason for concern, indicating that attention must be paid to the qualitative aspect of the changes, which we consider most crucial. Only 7 students responded "low", which is negative and must be considered.

Figure 11. Students' Assessment of the Effectiveness of Applying Pedagogical Predictions

- a) High – 23.91 %
- b) Moderate – 71.01 %
- c) Low – 5,07 %

Question 5: Do you think that pedagogical predictions help to adapt educational programs and methodologies to the demands of the modern world?

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) Partly

More than half of the surveyed students recognize improvements in educational programs and methodologies in response to contemporary demands. While 47 students see the changes but not wholly, 11 students do not see any changes at all, which is a negative response. However, since there are indeed improvements in educational programs and teaching methods at our university, we believe these students fall into the indifferent category.

Figure 12. Students' Opinions on the Assistance of Pedagogical Predictions in Improving Educational Programs and Methodologies

- a) Yes – 57,97%
- b) No – 7,97%
- c) Partly – 34,05%

Question 6: Do you see any specific challenges and obstacles in the application of pedagogical futurology predicting approaches in the field of education?

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) Partly

We have the following distribution of responses to this question: 41 students (29.71%) answered "yes," 35 students (25.36%) answered "no," and 62 students (44.92%) answered "partly."

Of the surveyed 138 students, 41 surprisingly find that predictive approaches in education, which can also prevent specific issues, could hinder education development. This clearly indicates that these students are not aware of what pedagogical futurology is and its objectives. Here, we also reiterate that there is a lack of awareness. As for the "no" and "partly" responses, we can say that 97 students are convinced that pedagogical predictions not only do not harm but help in the development of education.

Figure 13. Students' opinions on specific barriers in the application of pedagogical futurology predicting approaches

- a) Yes – 29.71%
- b) No – 25.36 %
- c) Partly – 44.92 %

Question 7: Are additional resources or support necessary for more practical application of predictive methods of pedagogical futurology in education?

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) Partly

Out of the surveyed 138 students, 93 students (67.39%) answered "yes," 9 students (6.52%) answered "no," and 36 students (26.08%) answered "partly." These percentages indicate that the overwhelming majority of students, 67%, believe in the importance and effectiveness of educational predictions, finding that additional resources and support are necessary for more effective implementation of predictive methods in education. The 36 students who answered "partly" believe that existing resources can be moderately supported, while the nine students who answered "no" think that the existing resources are sufficient. We think this is not about conserving resources but a lack of awareness regarding predictive methods. This further confirms our view that today's students need to be informed about the predictions for the future of education in the 21st century, which not only opens new directions but also preempts upcoming challenges.

Figure 14. Students' Opinions on the Need for Additional Resources or Support for More Effective Application of Predictive Methods in Education

- a) Yes - 67,39 %
- b) No - 6,52 %
- c) Partly – 26,08 %

Conclusion

Predictions of pedagogical futurology about the future of education contribute to developing more effective management strategies for educational systems. Predictions of pedagogical futurology help ensure a more efficient and quality education that meets contemporary demands, preparing specialists capable of addressing future challenges.

Therefore, we believe that it is essential to undertake additional courses related to Pedagogical predictions for students of all the faculties.

The responses to sociological surveys on pedagogical predictions among lecturers lead to the conclusion that it is necessary to enhance lecturers' awareness of

the critical role of pedagogical predictions in the development process of education. This can be achieved through non-formal education, specifically through training courses.

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